

TALANOIA

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Deliverable 5.7: Policy playbook for transformational adaptation in water management

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Executive summary

This policy playbook offers practical guidance for transformational adaptation in water management across the Mediterranean, promoting systemic and radical change in how water is managed, how incentives for water conservation are designed, and how knowledge about water-related risks and opportunities is generated and used in decision-making. It is grounded in the experience and lessons of the Talanoa Water project, funded by the PRIMA programme, and draws on six pilot basins in Southern Europe and the Middle East and North Africa (Spain, France, Italy, Lebanon, Tunisia, and Egypt). Through these pilots, the project team combined analytical work, modelling, and inclusive policy dialogue to explore how water systems can adapt under accelerating climate stress.

The playbook starts from the recognition that Mediterranean water systems face recurring and compounding stress patterns: chronic water scarcity combined with peak demand, groundwater depletion and salinisation, ecological degradation, and failures in inter-sectoral reallocation during droughts. Rather than cataloguing solutions, this playbook focuses on the capabilities required to make transformational adaptation possible. Capabilities are understood as the practical abilities of water governance actors to plan, decide, implement, and sustain adaptation under uncertainty. The report groups these capabilities into three interconnected domains: technical, institutional, and financial. Together, they form the enabling conditions that determines whether adaptation remains reactive and piecemeal or becomes strategic, scalable, and resilient over time.

On the technical side, the playbook addresses the importance of integrated data management, climate risk analysis, stress testing, and monitoring. Across the pilots, building shared data spaces, combining Earth Observation with local information, and developing repeatable analytical workflows allow authorities to move from qualitative narratives of scarcity to evidence-based diagnostics. Stress testing allocation rules and infrastructure systems through climate storylines showcased how decision-makers can anticipate cascading risks rather than plan only for average conditions. Robust monitoring systems, including the use of remote sensing to assess actual water use, is essential for compliance, learning, and adaptive management.

On the institutional side, we show that fragmentation of mandates, weak coordination, limited enforcement, and short political time horizons are among the main reasons why adaptation remains incremental. The playbook emphasises capabilities for inclusive governance, coordination, accountability, and learning. It highlights Talanoa dialogues as a powerful method for building trust, shared understanding, and ownership in contexts where reform is contested or politically sensitive. When combined with serious games and iterative engagement, Talanoa processes helped stakeholders confront trade-offs, explore pathways, and move toward feasible, collectively supported reforms.

On the financial side, the playbook identifies structural barriers that prevent water adaptation from scaling: insufficient cost recovery, difficulty in valuing non-market benefits, budgetary competition, and short investment horizons. Finance gaps are essentially insufficient capabilities to structuring finance, managing risk, and aligning incentives with long-term resilience goals. We illustrate how hydro-economic modelling, pricing reform, insurance instruments, and market mechanisms can support equitable and efficient allocation. We also argue that nature-based solutions remain hard to scale not because of lack of interest, but because of limited capacity to design viable business innovation models, internalise ecosystem service values, and link them to finance and insurance mechanisms.

The playbook situates these insights within a broader policy landscape, including the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, the Global Goal on Adaptation, and emerging initiatives such as CLIMAAX, Pathways2Resilience, and the European Water Resilience Investment Accelerator. These programmes provide targeted support and cascading funds which help regions move from risk awareness to implementation-ready adaptation pathways.

In the playbook we argue that transformational adaptation is not defined by radical measures alone, but by the capabilities that allow societies to sequence reforms, manage trade-offs, mobilise investment, and sustain action under uncertainty. The nine capabilities presented across technical, institutional, and financial domains are not exhaustive, but provide a practical starting point. We encourage further research, training, and experimentation, and suggest that these capabilities could be translated into indicators to support monitoring of adaptation progress at the river basin scale.

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1 Introduction

This *transformational adaptation policy playbook* is a practical guide designed to help decision-makers and stakeholders across the Mediterranean move from isolated, incremental improvements to system-level change in how water resources are planned, governed, financed, and managed under climate stress. Because Mediterranean communities face different combinations of challenges and operate under diverse legal, political, economic, social, and environmental conditions, the playbook does not offer a single “best” solution. No *one-size-fits-all* approach can be universally applied across the region. Instead, the playbook sets out actionable *technical, institutional, and financial* capabilities that together create the enabling conditions for transformational change. These conditions support diagnosing root causes, navigating trade-offs, building coalitions, and sequencing reforms and investments so that adaptation becomes scalable, durable, and locally appropriate.

This policy playbook is a result of, and a collection of, **insights gathered through the Talanoa Water project**¹ (funded by the PRIMA² programme). With the playbook we aim at bridging knowledge from science to policy to support transformational adaptation in water management. The playbook is designed to help public agencies, basin authorities, municipalities, utilities, and ministries seeking to move beyond incremental improvements and enable system-level change in the way water resources and services are governed, financed, and managed under climate change. Throughout the project, this work was guided by the principles of the *Talanoa Dialogue*, which provided a structured and inclusive method to support policy learning and co-design.

Talanoa water dialogues are a structured and flexible approach to inclusive, trust-based policy dialogue. In the context of this playbook, they are designed to support transformational adaptation to water scarcity under climate change. In the Talanoa Water project, the dialogues were implemented through six pilot *water laboratories* across the Mediterranean (Spain, France, Italy, Lebanon, Tunisia, and Egypt), each convening a local stakeholder platform including public authorities, water users, technical agencies, and civil society. The policy dialogues followed a shared narrative logic, gradually moving from “*Where are we now?*” to “*Where do we want to go?*” and “*How do we get there?*”. This process was implemented through iterative workshops and targeted engagement activities (such as serious policy game) that combined evidence and modelling inputs with stakeholder knowledge and lived experience. The dialogues also created a space for developing a shared understanding of underlying, context-specific challenges, co-designing adaptation options, collectively discussing pros and cons and trade-offs, and progressively refining strategies through repeated rounds of interaction.

¹ *Talanoa Water Dialogue for transformational adaptation to water scarcity under climate change, 2021-2025*, <https://talanoawater.com/>

² *Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA)* is an international research and innovation programme that supports cooperation between European and Mediterranean countries to address shared challenges, especially around water scarcity, food systems, and the agri-food value chain.

This type of participatory process is most suitable for planning transformative adaptation in water management because it addresses the key bottlenecks that often prevent system-level change: fragmented mandates, contested priorities, low trust, and limited ownership of system-wide decisions. By creating a non-confrontational environment that encourages collaboration rather than blame, Talanoa dialogues help stakeholders move beyond incremental measures and engage with deeper reforms, such as allocation rules, governance redesign, investment priorities, and mechanisms for the fair distribution of benefits and costs. They link long-term climate risk understanding to operational constraints and political feasibility, enabling actors to develop shared visions and credible pathways for implementation. In this way, Talanoa dialogues are not only a consultation tool, but also a practical method to build consensus, strengthen legitimacy, and sustain the partnerships required to deliver transformation at scale.

But what do we mean by transformational adaptation in a water management context? Listening to contemporary policy debates, one might think that only “*transformational*” matters, while “*incremental*” is not sufficient or ambitious enough. Let’s be very clear that this is *not* the case. Incremental adaptation remains essential in many places and for many reasons: to improve efficiency and day-to-day operations in the short term, especially under emergency conditions where immediate vulnerabilities are high. *Transformational adaptation* is necessary when incremental solutions ***no longer keep pace with the scale, persistence, or complexity of climate and socio-economic challenges***. In practice, transformative solutions refer to system-level changes that address the underlying causes of water insecurity, such as unsustainable demand, outdated allocation rules, fragmented governance, incentives that degrade rather than protect ecosystems, and misaligned financial frameworks, **rather than only treating symptoms** through temporary fixes. They often involve politically and institutionally challenging decisions, including redesigning governance and accountability frameworks, shifting investment priorities, revisiting fairness and cost-sharing arrangements, and rethinking the role of nature, infrastructure, and demand management in securing water services. In this sense, transformational adaptation is about a step change in how water is managed, so that systems remain viable, equitable, and resilient under a changing climate.

But while there is broad agreement on the need to move beyond “*business as usual*”, it is far from clear what transformational adaptation looks like in practice, or what distinguishes transformational from sizeable but still incremental improvements. To explore this topic, the UNFCCC secretariat, the body supporting the UN Climate Convention and the Paris Agreement, commissioned a technical paper³ to clarify how transformational adaptation is defined, interpreted, and assessed across sectors and scales. The report confirmed that transformational adaptation involves changing the *fundamental* attributes of social-ecological systems, rather than only optimizing existing practices, and stresses that adaptation sits on a *continuum* where incremental actions can sometimes accumulate into transformative outcomes. It also

³ UNFCCC, 2024. Technical paper on transformational adaptation (Technical Paper). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/tp2024_08.pdf

emphasized that “*transformational*” does not automatically mean “*better*” or “*sufficient*”: low transformation may be appropriate for some risks, while highly transformational actions may still be insufficient to offset others. The report suggested practical dimensions to recognize transformative change, including *depth of change* (novel practices and structural reform), *scale* (system-wide adoption), *speed* of change, and the ability to challenge or overcome ‘soft’ *adaptation limits*, as well as the importance of adaptive sustainability (robustness and persistence over time). In this sense, transformational adaptation is best understood as a **deliberate pathway of change that combines institutional, financial, technological, and behavioural shifts**, anchored in context-specific priorities and equity considerations, to expand the “*solution space*” for managing climate risks before hard limits are reached.

Others have also tried to pin down what transformational water adaptation means in practice. The *Global Commission on the Economics of Water*, for example, advocated a fundamental reframing of how water is valued, governed, and allocated, arguing that incremental efficiency improvements would not be sufficient unless embedded in deeper structural reforms⁴. It emphasised the hydrological cycle as a global common good, highlighting the importance of managing not only “blue water” (rivers, lakes, and aquifers) but also “green water” (soil moisture and vegetation) and the atmospheric connections that link regions. Based on this framing, the Commission called for *mission-oriented* water governance, including revisiting allocation rules and water rights, and aligning permits, contracts, and finance with shared societal outcomes. It also stressed the role of equity and justice in water management and proposed “*Just Water Partnerships*” to mobilise long-term investment and coordinate public and private action toward water security and ecosystem integrity.

In this playbook, we argue that **what makes a pathway transformational is not only the type of intervention or reform selected, but the enabling conditions that allow it to be designed, adopted, and implemented consistently over time**. These enabling conditions include the technical, institutional, and financial capabilities needed to manage trade-offs, coordinate actors, mobilise investment, and sustain delivery under climate stress. For this reason, the playbook focuses less on compiling “solutions” and more on strengthening the capabilities that make transformational change possible.

As capabilities we understood in a broad and practical sense the ability of a water governance system and its actors to plan, decide, implement, and sustain adaptation under changing and uncertain conditions. We group these capacities into three interconnected categories. **Technical capabilities** refer to the ability to generate and use decision-relevant knowledge, including data, monitoring, climate information, modelling, forecasting, and operational tools that support planning and risk management. **Institutional and organisational capabilities** include the ability to coordinate across actors and scales, define clear mandates and responsibilities, enforce rules, engage stakeholders, and maintain effective governance

⁴ Global Commission on the Economics of Water, 2024. The Economics of Water: Valuing the Hydrological Cycle as a Global Common Good. Global Commission on the Economics of Water.
<https://economicsofwater.watercommission.org/report/economics-of-water.pdf>

arrangements over time. **Financial capabilities** refer to the ability to mobilise and allocate resources for adaptation, including investment planning, cost recovery, incentives, risk-sharing and risk-transfer instruments, and the long-term funding needed for implementation, operation, and maintenance. Together, these capabilities form the enabling foundation that determines whether adaptation remains a set of isolated measures or becomes a scalable and durable transformational shift in water management.

This playbook is structured as follow: In **Section 2**, we revisit climate change impacts across the Mediterranean, introduce common typologies of adaptation actions, and describe the challenges encountered in the project’s pilot basins. We also explain why transformational adaptation is increasingly necessary and present examples of large-scale programmes that help create the conditions for policy change. In **Section 3**, we examine the technical, institutional, and financial barriers to adaptation, along with ways to address them, drawing primarily on insights from our own research and complementing them with relevant examples from other sources where appropriate.

This playbook is not a technical manual, nor a climate science report. It does not aim to provide detailed engineering designs, modelling protocols, or exhaustive reviews of climate impacts. Rather, it seeks to inspire and guide decision-makers and practitioners who are navigating complex choices, drawing on our experiences and lessons learned from the field, and from emerging practices. The playbook is meant to support reflection and dialogue, and help readers ask better questions, and identify where and how to build the capabilities needed for a change.

2 Landscape of adaptation challenges and solutions in the Mediterranean

Water management challenges and risks across the Mediterranean, including both Southern Europe and the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, are characterised by **a common set of recurring stress patterns** driven by long-standing anthropogenic pressures exacerbated by climate change⁵. A dominant pattern is the growing mismatch between chronic water deficits and peak demand, where declining summer availability coincides with high water demand for irrigation, urban consumption, and mass tourism, which creates persistent scarcity and recurrent “*crisis management*” mode. Another pattern is the accelerating depletion of groundwater, which serves as buffer during droughts, and which in many places is no longer sufficiently replenished fast enough and which is also affected by salinisation and quality degradation, particularly in coastal areas and intensively farmed zones. A third pattern is ecological degradation, where reduced river flows, altered seasonality, pollution, and over-abstraction undermine freshwater ecosystems and the services they provide. These patterns of pressures expose the limits of existing governance systems through failures in inter-sectoral allocation under stress: when water is scarce, competing needs across agriculture, cities, energy, and ecosystems become harder to reconcile, and rigid or fragmented allocation rules struggle to deliver fair and effective decisions. Together, these stresses create a cycle in which *scarcity, overuse, and ecosystem decline reinforce one another* and make transformational adaptation increasingly important to secure essential water services in the region. In some areas across the Mediterranean, these conditions reach the level of *water bankruptcy*⁶, a persistent state of over-commitment and depletion with limited capacity to return to previous baselines, which can only be addressed through long-term demand rebalancing, allocation reforms, and the protection of strategic reserves. At that point, transformation becomes unavoidable, and the key question is what form it will take. One path is chaotic disallocation, where uncoordinated and reactive water reallocations occur, often creating inefficiencies, inequities, and sustainability problems. The other is organised disallocation, where transformational reallocations are planned and governed to align with societal goals, manage trade-offs, and minimise economic, social, and environmental losses.

⁵ Fader, M., Giupponi, C., Burak, S., Dakhlaoui, H., Koutroulis, A., Lange, M.A., Llasat, M.C., Pulido-Velazquez, D., Sanz-Cobeña, A., 2020. First Mediterranean Assessment Report – Chapter 3.1: Resources – Water.

Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7101074>;

Caretta, M.A., A. Mukherji, M. Arfanuzzaman, R.A. Betts, A. Gelfan, Y. Hirabayashi, T.K. Lissner, J. Liu, E. Lopez Gunn, R. Morgan, S. Mwanga, and S. Supratid, 2022: Water. In: Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Löschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 551–712, doi:10.1017/9781009325844.006.

⁶ United Nations University Institute for Water, Environment and Health (UNU INWEH), Madani, K., 2026. Global Water Bankruptcy: Living Beyond Our Hydrological Means in the Post Crisis Era. United Nations University Institute for Water, Environment and Health (UNU INWEH). <https://doi.org/10.53328/INR26KAM001>

These **common stress patterns are felt across all Talanoia Water pilot areas**, although with different intensities and in different combinations depending on hydro-climatic conditions, land use, and governance and social conditions. In **Spain**, where the project focused on the *Cega catchment* (which is one of the few non-regulated basins in the country), rapid expansion of groundwater-fed horticulture, limited groundwater recharge, and increasing intensity of drought conditions created mounting stress on deep aquifers and raised questions around how to reduce demand, scale groundwater recharge solutions, and strengthen cost recovery mechanisms. In **France**, the pilot in the *Aude and Hérault departments* addressed growing water scarcity in vineyard-dominated areas, where supplementary irrigation is increasingly used to cope with drought risks, but where overallocation, environmental degradation, and salinity constraints made it difficult to balance agricultural needs with ecosystem protection. In **Italy**, the pilot in the upper Secchia catchment (a right tributary to the Po River) in the Emilia-Romagna focused on more severe droughts and uneven impacts between upstream and downstream users exposed the limits of polycentric allocation and charging systems with insufficient inter-regional coordination, bringing allocation rules and institutional reform to the core of adaptation planning. In **Lebanon**, the *Upper Litani catchment* case combined climatic stress with deep socio-economic pressures, including longstanding groundwater overexploitation, growing competition between irrigation and urban use, and the additional demand associated with a large refugee influx, amplifying the need for improved water accounting, clearer allocation choices, and trust-building across institutions. In **Tunisia**, the *Jeffara catchment* (Medenine–Djerba–Zarzis area) faces persistent aridity and groundwater overuse, compounded by saline intrusion; the pilot also highlighted the dependence of domestic supply and tourism on non-conventional water sources, network efficiency challenges, and the limited reuse of treated wastewater despite its potential value for reducing pressure on aquifers and supporting agriculture. Finally, in **Egypt**, the *Lower Nile Basin / Nile Delta* pilot focused on systemic risks linked to water scarcity, waterlogging and soil salinity, and upstream uncertainty related to developments such as the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam and their implications for downstream water availability, making adaptation priorities closely connected to agricultural productivity, monitoring, and salinity management.

To some extent, the **strategies and priority solutions** identified to address these challenges were also similar across the pilot areas. For example, most pilots explored options to modernise irrigation systems, such as shifting to drip and other efficient technologies, adopting deficit irrigation, and using climate-smart scheduling and advisory tools, to reduce losses and sustain productivity. Many basins also considered non-conventional water sources to relieve pressure on overstretched rivers and aquifers, including the reuse of treated wastewater (in France, Tunisia, and Lebanon) and, where relevant, the safe use of brackish or saline water through desalination or biosaline farming practices (especially in Tunisia and Egypt). Improving water storage and buffering capacity was another recurring theme: some pilots explored new surface or aquifer storage options, such as dams or managed aquifer recharge, while others focused on optimising existing reservoirs and conjunctive use strategies. On the demand side, several pilots assessed crop and land management measures, including shifts toward less water-intensive crops, soil moisture

conservation, and agro-ecological practices to maintain yields under drier conditions. In parallel, multiple pilots examined economic and incentive-based instruments, such as drought insurance funds, revised pricing and tariff structures, and water trading mechanisms, to support behavioural change and mobilise investment. Finally, all pilots stressed the enabling role of stronger governance and integrated planning, including more inclusive allocation processes, clearer and more climate-robust rules (e.g., permits and environmental flows), and improved data and modelling capacity to support transparent, evidence-based decisions. Together, **these measures form the backbone of a Mediterranean adaptation strategies**: a portfolio of interventions that combines technical innovation, diversification of supply sources, demand management, and governance reform to build resilience at scale.

Many have tried to produce a **typology or classification of adaptation actions** in water resource management. Among them, Elgendy et al.⁷ provided a structured review of adaptation strategies and grouped them into a practical set of categories that reflect how water managers actually intervene in systems under climate stress. Their typology distinguishes between (i) *institutional and policy measures* (e.g., regulations, agreements, and coordination mechanisms, including for transboundary basins), (ii) *resilience- and capacity-oriented approaches* (including preparedness, social resilience building, and community-based coping practices), and (iii) *ecosystem-based adaptation* (such as watershed restoration, reforestation, riparian buffers, wetlands, and coastal nature-based protections). For strategies linked to engineered water systems, the review highlights options aimed at closing the *supply–demand gap* through *supply augmentation and conservation* (e.g., dams, rainwater harvesting), *demand management* (e.g., leakage control, metering, pricing, land-use planning, irrigation efficiency, and policy reforms), and *water reuse* (notably treated wastewater reuse supported by enabling policies). *System reoperation and optimisation* is also a major adaptation category, with emphasis on updating reservoir operating rules and control curves, along with the category dedicated to *allocation adjustments*, under which allocation rules or “water year type” classifications are revised to maintain performance under changing hydrological regimes. The review also recognises adaptation domain for *urban drainage* and *flood mitigation*, characterised by low-impact development and best management practices (e.g., bioretention, infiltration systems, porous pavements, wetlands).

Building on these shared measures and strategies, the **next question is what makes adaptation truly transformational in water management**. Is it the intrinsic novelty of a measure in a given context, or rather the scale, speed, and consistency with which it is implemented? In practice, transformational adaptation is rarely defined by a single “*radical*” solution that can be copied from elsewhere. The difference between serious reform planning and wishful thinking often lies in recognising that strategies which appear successful in one basin may not be politically feasible, institutionally viable, or financially sustainable in another.

⁷ Elgendy, M., Hassini, S., Coulibaly, P., 2024. Review of Climate Change Adaptation Strategies in Water Management. J. Hydrol. Eng. 29, 03123001. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JHYEFF.HEENG-6014>

According to the **Europe’s State of Environment Report 2025**⁸, uneven progress has been made towards reaching the water policy goals: while progress was made on safe drinking water and sanitation, other objectives related to water quantity, ecosystem health, and pollution are not being met at the required pace, and the impacts of climate change weigh in on this underperformance. The report estimates that water stress affects around 30% of Europe’s territory and 34% of the population, with growing scarcity risks affecting particularly Southern Europe. Progress on ecological objectives is limited too: in 2021 only 37% of surface water bodies reached good or high ecological status, and aquatic ecosystem degradation is recognised as a threat to Europe’s water resilience. Agriculture remains a major driver of both quantitative and qualitative pressures, through over-abstraction as well as nutrient and pesticide pollution, which continue to undermine the achievement of core EU water objectives. The report supports our perspective that even a well-designed and structured water policy framework may lag behind accelerating risks due to limited technical, institutional, and financial capabilities.

Throughout this playbook, we refer to one of the European Union’s main transformational adaptation programmes: the **EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change**⁹. Adopted in 2021, the Mission is part of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, dedicated to advancing interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral research and innovation for climate resilience. Within the Mission, national and subnational public authorities work alongside research and innovation organisations as equal partners to strengthen Europe’s capacity to anticipate, prepare for, and respond to climate risks and shocks. As the innovation arm of the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, the Mission pursues ambitious objectives, including empowering local and regional authorities with the tools, data, and knowledge needed to access, interpret, and apply climate risk information, and to design and implement robust, science-based adaptation strategies and investments. The EU Adaptation Mission has inspired other initiatives aimed at accelerating adaptation action on the ground, such as the **Adaptation Accelerator Hub** led by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)¹⁰. This platform brings together public and private actors to co-design and scale investment-ready adaptation solutions, offers tools for financing and implementation, and supports countries and subnational authorities in building bankable pipelines of resilience projects. It reflects a growing recognition, shared with the EU Mission, that bridging the gap between climate risk knowledge and real-world action requires not only data and planning tools, but also directed support to mobilise finance and unlock implementation capacity.

⁸ European Environment Agency, 2025. Europe’s environment 2025: knowledge for resilience, prosperity and sustainability. Publications Office, LU. <https://doi.org/10.2800/3817344>

⁹ European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2021. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on European missions. Publications Office, LU. <https://doi.org/10.2777/084922>

¹⁰ UNDP, n.d. The Adaptation Accelerator Hub | UNDP Climate Change Adaptation [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.adaptation-undp.org/adaptationacceleratorhub> (accessed 1.27.26).

3 Unlocking large-scale transformational adaptation

3.1 Strengthen technical capabilities

3.1.1 What blocks progress (technical bottlenecks)

Technical barriers to adaptation in water management are often framed as “*implementation challenges*,” but in reality they sit much deeper: they mediate what decision-makers can *see, measure, test, and ultimately change* in complex water systems. A most recurring barrier is the **lack of adequate data and monitoring**, which limits the ability to design and operate water systems under increasing variability and extremes. Water resource systems cannot be effectively planned without reliable information on water quantity, quality, temporal variability, and demand, yet many agencies lack the capacity to collect and analyse the data needed for operational and strategic decisions¹¹. Even where data exist, they are often fragmented into siloed datasets (e.g., flood, groundwater, water quality), limiting integrated assessment across sectors and scales.

Another major barrier relates to limitations in **modelling capability and usability**: hydrological and allocation models may be technically advanced, but they can be difficult to calibrate, validate, and translate into actionable insights for policy and investment decisions, especially as climate change makes past hydrological records less representative of future conditions. Decision-making is constrained by uncertainties and imperfect performance assessment, where authorities lack robust frameworks to test whether proposed measures will remain effective, or even to evaluate whether existing interventions are delivering the expected outcomes.

A third cluster of barriers concerns **technology readiness and supporting infrastructure**: many promising solutions (from advanced sensing and remote monitoring to reuse technologies and digital optimisation tools) require not only technical equipment, but also trained personnel, maintenance systems, interoperability standards, and long-term operational budgets, conditions that are often weak or missing in practice.

The fourth barrier relates to the uneven **capacity to adopt and govern innovation**, including digital tools and AI-based systems: while these technologies are increasingly promoted as solutions for forecasting, emergency response, and operational efficiency, their effectiveness still depends on data availability, digital literacy, and governance safeguards, and they can introduce new vulnerabilities through malfunction, design errors, or cyber risks.

Finally, technical barriers are not only about “tools” but also about the ability to link technical analysis to real-world decision processes: as highlighted in our options paper¹², technical and scientific capabilities

¹¹ UN Water (Ed.), 2024. Water for prosperity and peace, The United Nations World Water Development Report. UNESCO, Paris.

¹² Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Soriano, G., Mysiak, J., Graveline, N., 2024. Options paper, deliverable D4.4: PRIMA Foundation.

interact with institutional arrangements and incentives, meaning that even well-designed measures can fail when the system lacks the technical capacity to monitor compliance, enforce allocation rules, or sustain learning over time. These barriers illustrate why transformational adaptation is not simply a question of selecting better measures, but of strengthening the technical capabilities that allow to **anticipate, diagnose, and manage water scarcity and extremes** in a credible, sustained, and scalable way.

3.1.2 What to do now (tools, data, and operational solutions)

Building capacities for access, management, and integrated analysis of diverse datasets. Sound, evidence-based water resource management relies on data and information from multiple sources, managed by different actors and reported at different scales and frequencies. These include observational data (e.g., weather, river flows, water quality, environmental conditions, water withdrawals and use, and infrastructure losses), model-based outputs (e.g., climate projections and predictions, and modelled river discharge or aquifer recharge), and administrative and accounting information (e.g., abstraction permits and water-use records). Capabilities to organise data, document quality, govern access, ensure regular updates, and stimulate reuse and the development of tailored knowledge (e.g., climate and adaptation services) are essential in increasingly complex and digital economies. Modern data and information systems increasingly rely on federated architectures, where data providers retain control of their datasets which are brought together through shared standards, interfaces, and rules for access and quality assurance, referred to as data spaces. **Data spaces** are organised environments that make it easier for organisations to share, access, combine, and reuse data by providing the necessary tools and services and by establishing clear governance rules for interoperability, quality assurance, security, and responsible use. In EU policy, the concept has been strongly promoted through the 2020 European Strategy for Data¹³, supported by legislation and regulations that facilitate the reuse of public-sector information and define access conditions for “high-value datasets.” But data spaces become transformative only when combined with a “community of practice” where authorities, utilities, research organisations, service providers, and users can co-develop datasets, indicators, and applications, and gradually translate technical capacity into operational routines. Therefore, the data space is not only a technical platform, but an enabling condition for lasting system change, supporting transparency, coordination, accountability, and learning across the institutions responsible for delivering water security under climate stress.

Climate risk data have never been easier to access and analyse, including through cloud-based environments such as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), dedicated data platforms such as the Climate Data Store and the Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) such as [WEKEO](#), and emerging initiatives such as Destination Earth and its digital twins. Climate observations and reanalyses, short- to long-term predictions, and projections across different emissions pathways are now available from multiple models, enabling multi-model ensembles and providing pre-computed climate impact

¹³ European Commission, 2020. A European strategy for data. European Commission.

drivers. However, harnessing this wealth of accessible information and translating it into decision-relevant insights for local and context-specific water management requires technical capabilities that are often not yet available within the organisations responsible for water resources planning and operations. For this reason, the EU Mission on Adaptation launched CLIMAAX¹⁴ to **democratise climate risk analytics** by combining open, reusable [technical workflows](#) with direct support to subnational governments, helping foster an innovation ecosystem in climate services. In practice, CLIMAAX provides local and regional authorities with an open-source toolbox of risk workflows (Python-based Jupyter Notebooks), hosted via a dedicated ECMWF JupyterHub, covering key hazards such as floods, heatwaves, wildfires, and drought risk and related impacts. In parallel, it offers cascading funds, enabling regions to mobilise local expertise and contract specialised support to apply these tools in real decision contexts. In doing so, climate risk assessment moves from a one-off exercise to a repeatable local capability, while strengthening the broader ecosystem of practitioners and service providers building on shared, transparent methods and data.

Across the Talanoa Water pilots, our modelling expert team focused on strengthening local technical capabilities by establishing consistent analytical baselines and filling key data and modelling gaps that limit decision-making. This work combined available in situ observations (e.g., meteorology, flows, reservoir information, abstractions where accessible) with Earth Observation products. Through repeatable workflows and quality checks, the team enabled pilots to quantify basin water balances, identify where and how water is depleted, and move from qualitative narratives of scarcity to evidence-based diagnostics. In parallel, the project strengthened the foundations for data use through a shared Data Sourcebook and metadata framework, helping pilots document available datasets, identify constraints, and support interoperability across basins. Furthermore, in the Italian pilot basin, the enhancement of technical capabilities enabled local actors to *design climate service* combining short- to medium-range weather and climate predictions to forecast river flows and their subsequent allocation among water users, becoming a cornerstone of the revised water resource management plan.

Building capacities to anticipate service disruption, stress-test critical infrastructure, and assess resilience to shocks. The full value of integrated data spaces, and the capabilities they help to build, lies in what they enable: basin and regional authorities can move from one-off studies to continuous risk and performance intelligence, supporting early warning, drought allocation decisions, asset maintenance, and investment prioritisation. They also provide the ground for more advanced tools such as stress testing of water management provisions, climate-informed operating rules, scenario modelling, and decision support, all of which depend on stable data pipelines and credible baselines. Stress testing goes beyond planning for “average” future conditions and instead examines whether key elements of water management, such as allocation rules, operating procedures, drought plans, and the performance of critical infrastructure, remain effective under plausible but disruptive scenarios. One practical way to do this is by

¹⁴ Climate risk and vulnerability assessment framework and toolbox, Horizon Europe 2023-2027, <https://www.climaax.eu/>

combining quantitative risk assessment with narrative storylines that trace how hazards may interact, occur in sequence, and cascade across sectors and locations, potentially amplifying impacts through bottlenecks, feedback effects, and external stressors (for example, a health emergency or energy disruption). This storyline-based framing makes stress tests more decision-relevant by clarifying the triggers, the propagation pathways, and the conditions under which disruptions become systemic, helping decision-makers prioritise reforms and investments that strengthen resilience not only to known risks, but also to complex and compounding shocks.

In the Italian pilot, a storylines approach was used to stress-test how water governance and key actors could evolve under increasing drought and climate volatility. The storylines contrasted a “*permanent emergency*” pathway, where repeated crises shift water management into reactive mode, with emergency task forces replacing ordinary planning, aggravating inequalities, and encouraging fragmented private coping, with a reform pathway centred on *institutional resilience and adaptive innovation*, where stress tests, climate services, and experimentation support early coordinated action. Parallel storylines explored how water boards might either pursue “*efficiency-first*” upgrades that reduce losses but undermine recharge and ecological functions or evolve into “*efficiency brokers*” and *ecological stewards* that mediate allocation, incentivise retention and recharge, and integrate ecosystem services into irrigation management. By framing alternative futures for farmers, utilities, and citizens, the pilot showcased how storylines can translate climate risk into concrete governance and investment choices, showing what reforms help avoid lock-in to crisis response and instead enable planned, scalable adaptation.

Building capacities for monitoring operational compliance and adaptation performance. Monitoring compliance with agreed water management rules and assessing progress on adaptation are essential technical capabilities, yet they are far from being guaranteed in practice. A concrete example of how these capabilities can be developed in practice comes from the Spanish pilot, where modelling and remote sensing were used to estimate actual irrigation water use and identify unaccounted abstractions, supporting more realistic compliance strategies¹⁵. In the pilot basin, which is under heavy irrigation pressure, our project team showed that official records mainly reflect theoretical allocations (what is permitted), while actual withdrawals can be significantly higher, which raised concerns about unpermitted water use not captured in official registers. The gap was assessed by estimating actual evapotranspiration from a combination of local monitoring data and remote sensing, complemented with tools to quantify irrigation demand. The analysis also produced land-use and crop maps from Earth Observation time series, applying classification trees and farm-scale machine learning to improve spatial attribution. Additional work tested land-surface temperature products and downscaling methods (using Sentinel-2

¹⁵ Jaafar, H., Hazimeh, R., Mourad, R., Pérez-Blanco, C.D., González-López, H., Debolini, M., Dorchie, D., Graveline, N., Mazzoli, P., Bagli, S., Renzi, F., Shehata, A., Ben Hamouda, M.F., 2023. Deliverable 2.2: Water Accounting Database V2.0. PRIMA Foundation.

reflectance and Sentinel-3 radiances) to increase resolution and support water-stress detection, strengthening classification and water accounting.

A sound *monitoring, evaluation and learning* (MEL) framework for adaptation in water management should combine a comparable core set of indicators with locally relevant metrics, embedded in a clear path-to-impacts connects actions to outcomes and longer-term benefits. The UNFCCC process on the Global Goal on Adaptation¹⁶ recognises water resource management as a core adaptation priority, with targets to reduce climate-driven water scarcity, strengthen resilience to water-related hazards, and improve access to climate-resilient water and sanitation services. It has also launched dedicated work to develop and refine indicators for tracking collective progress, so that adaptation outcomes and water security can be assessed consistently over time. The agreed indicators¹⁷ cover both water scarcity and service resilience, including water stress levels, water-use efficiency, and the share of critical water and sanitation infrastructure that is resilient to climate hazards under different warming scenarios. They also capture planning and governance dimensions that are highly relevant for basin management, such as the proportion of basin area covered by a climate adaptation plan developed and implemented on the basis of different warming scenarios, together with service-oriented indicators for climate-resilient access to safe drinking water and safely managed sanitation. The indicators also acknowledge water quality and equity dimensions by including measures of ambient water quality for drinking water supply and the extent of efforts to improve services for populations disproportionately affected by climate change.

An example from the Upper Litani Basin shows how the FAO WaPOR (*the Water Productivity through Open access of Remotely sensed derived data*) model enabled to generate repeatable, spatial indicators of irrigation performance by estimating actual evapotranspiration (ET), biomass production, and derived water productivity¹⁸. Combined with basic economic information, this approach supports operational monitoring of where irrigation water is used efficiently, helping authorities target advisory services, prioritise investments, and track changes over time.

3.2 Enable Institutional Change and Coordination

3.2.1 Where governance fails (fragmentation and weak mandates)

Lack of institutional and organisational capabilities is often one of the main reasons why water adaptation remains incremental, even when technical solutions exist and growing water security risks call for urgent

¹⁶ UNFCCC, 2024. Report of the Conference of the Parties serving as the meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement on its fifth session, held in the United Arab Emirates from 30 November to 13 December 2023: Addendum (Decisions adopted). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

¹⁷ UNFCCC, 2025. Global goal on adaptation: Draft decision -/CMA.7 (Advance version). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC).

¹⁸ Jaafar, H., Karimi, P., Borgomeo, E., 2024. Economic irrigation water productivity of wheat and potato: An earth observation perspective on policy implications in the Litani Basin, Lebanon. *Agricultural Water Management* 306, 109180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2024.109180>

action. Institutional fragmentation is a common culprit: responsibilities for water allocation, infrastructure operation, environmental protection, agriculture, energy, spatial planning, and disaster risk management are spread across many organisations and levels of government from national to local), with weak mechanisms for co-ordination and policy coherence. This fragmentation leads to gaps, duplication or, even worse, unclear mandates, makes it difficult to take decisions at the right time and at the right scale, especially because hydrological boundaries do not follow the administrative ones. As highlighted by the OECD¹⁹, these governance failures tend to reinforce each other through a combination of *policy gaps* (cross-sector incoherence), *administrative gaps* (mismatched scales), and *objective gaps* (divergent priorities that inhibit synergies). In practice, this means that even when drought is recognised as systemic risk²⁰, adaptation is addressed by siloed interventions rather than through integrated basin-wide strategies and enforceable operating rules. Another key barrier is limited capacity to *translate strategies into implementation*: water laws and plans can exist on paper, but institutions may lack the procedures, resources, skills, and legitimacy to operationalise them in day-to-day decision-making. This includes limited enforcement capacity and weak monitoring and evaluation systems, which reduce accountability and allow non-compliance to persist. The OECD describes this as an **accountability gap**, where stakeholder engagement, compliance mechanisms, and enforcement are insufficient or irregular, which undermines trust and the credibility of water governance¹⁷. **Short time horizon of public decision-making** is another barrier, where electoral cycles and crisis-driven politics prioritise visible short-term measures over politically costly reforms such as revising allocation rules, restricting abstraction, reallocating water between sectors, or enforcing environmental flow standards. This “lock-in” dynamic means that organisations tend to preserve existing routines, infrastructure choices, and institutional arrangements until a major shock makes the need for change undeniable, and even then, reforms can stall due to institutional transaction costs and contested legitimacy. We have framed institutional capacity barriers²¹ as structural constraints that prevent transformational pathways from emerging, including rigid governance arrangements, weak co-ordination, low enforcement and compliance capacity, and limited ability to sustain reforms over time. These barriers show that transformational adaptation is not blocked primarily by lack of ideas, but by the absence of **governance capabilities** to align actors, manage trade-offs transparently, implement and enforce decisions consistently, and learn and adjust over time under increasing climate stress

It is worth to recall the OECD Principles on Water Governance²² which provide a practical framework for improving how water policies are designed and delivered, based on three complementary objectives: effectiveness (clear goals, roles and coordination), efficiency (maximising benefits at least cost, supported by sound financing and regulation), and trust and engagement (transparency, integrity, stakeholder

¹⁹ OECD, 2018. Implementing the OECD Principles on Water Governance: Indicator Framework and Evolving Practices, OECD Studies on Water. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264292659-en>

²⁰ EEA, 2024. European climate risk assessment. Publications Office, LU.

²¹ Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Soriano, G., Mysiak, J., Graveline, N., 2024. Deliverable 4.4: Options paper. PRIMA Foundation.

²² OECD, 2015. OECD Principles on Water Governance. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

participation, and fairness). These principles emphasise managing water at the right scale (often the basin), strengthening cross-sector coherence, building the capacity of responsible authorities, and ensuring that high-quality data and information guide decisions. The principles also stress the importance of robust regulatory frameworks, sustainable financing, innovation and learning, and regular monitoring and evaluation so governance systems can adapt over time.

3.2.2 What to reform (roles, rules, and accountability)

Building capabilities for inclusive, bottom-up water governance and all-of-society engagement. A defining characteristic of a modern public planning organisation is the capability to mobilise broad support for reform and to set clear terms of reference for implementing inclusive dialogue. There are multiple ways to build inclusive, bottom-up engagement in line with the all-of-society principle, including participatory policy planning and citizens’ assemblies, innovation labs and regulatory sandboxes, and other formats that enable stakeholders to co-design solutions and sustain collective ownership over implementation. Our experience from the Talanoa Water project points in particular to the value of Talanoa dialogues.

Talanoa for climate adaptation dialogues refers to a relational, story-based form of dialogue that originated in the Pacific Islands, where “talanoa” is a traditional way of holding inclusive conversations on shared issues in a respectful, non-confrontational space²³. This approach entered global climate policy through the UNFCCC Talanoa Dialogue launched under the Fiji COP23 Presidency. In climate adaptation, Talanoa is valuable because it creates the conditions for change where reform is difficult, contested, or politically costly: it helps involved actors build trust, develop a shared understanding of risks, constraints, and trade-offs, and connect scientific evidence with lived experience and local priorities²⁴. This translates into greater legitimacy and ownership, collective learning, coalition-building, and sustained cooperation, which are key enabling factors for moving beyond incremental measures.

Through our work we have learned that effective Talanoa-style dialogues are less about “*holding a workshop*” and more about **building the conditions for collective decision-making over time**. A good starting point is to invest early in stakeholder mapping and outreach, with broad representation across water managers, authorities, farmers, utilities, businesses, and civil society, including under-represented groups. The dialogue needs a clear **purpose** and a simple structure that keeps the discussion focused and progressive (for example, moving from “Where are we now?” to “Where do we want to go?” and “How do we get there?”), while still leaving space for local priorities to shape the agenda. **Trust and openness do not happen automatically**: they require a safe, non-confrontational setting, skilled facilitation, and clear ground rules that encourage listening, respect, and constructive exchange. We have also found that dialogues work best when they are iterative, not one-off: repeated sessions allow participants to deepen

²³ Hollis, S., Halapua, W., 2025. A climate change talanoa: exploring creative possibilities for a hopeful future. *AlterNative: An International Journal of Indigenous Peoples* 21, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11771801241310319>

²⁴ Hollis, S., 2025. Toward a Talanoa Way of Knowing: Relational Transformation for Environmental Sustainability and Climate Action. *Asia Pacific Viewpoint* apv.70020. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apv.70020>

their understanding of the system, revisit assumptions, and gradually refine options into realistic pathways.

Serious games can be powerful when adaptation choices involve uncertainty and trade-offs. When well designed, they create a “safe sandbox” where stakeholders can explore scenarios, test decisions, and experience the consequences of different strategies without real-world risk. The most important lesson is that the game itself is not the goal; the goal is the debrief and collective reflection where insights are translated into decision-relevant messages, priorities, and next steps. Games should be simple enough to be inclusive, realistic enough to be credible, and accompanied by guided discussion to connect outcomes to real policy and management choices. Across the project, this combination of dialogue and experiential learning proved effective in moving participants beyond abstract debates and toward a shared understanding of constraints, leverage points, and what feasible reform could look like.

We have also learned to pay **close attention to pitfalls** that can undermine the talanoa process. One risk is stakeholder fatigue or low participation, especially when key actors lack time or see no clear value in engagement. Another is allowing dialogues to drift into general discussion without convergence, which can be avoided by setting clear milestones (problem framing, option generation, prioritisation, feasibility checks). Power imbalances also matter: technical experts or institutional actors may unintentionally dominate, while others may hesitate to speak. Facilitators should actively design for inclusion, using small group work, rotating roles, or anonymous inputs when needed. The most critical pitfall probably is the absence of follow-up. If participants do not see how their contributions are captured and used, trust erodes quickly. Transparent documentation, feedback loops, and continuity between sessions are essential to sustain engagement and ensure dialogues lead to credible outputs, whether that is a shared risk framing, a prioritised portfolio of measures, or a pathway for implementation.

Building capabilities for equitable allocation and efficient water use starts from a simple reality: in water-scarce basins, adaptation is not only about “*finding more water*”, but about deciding who can use water, how much, when, and under what conditions. Water allocation regimes shape these decisions through a combination of laws, permits, operating rules, and governance arrangements that determine access to a shared resource pool and how shortages are managed. In practice, allocation often takes the form of *water entitlements* or *abstraction permits*, which may be granted for different durations (e.g., fixed-term licences or longer-term rights), and may come with obligations such as return-flow requirements, monitoring conditions, and restrictions during drought²⁵.

Reforming allocation is necessary when existing rules, often shaped by historical patterns and political equilibria, no longer reflect today’s risks, societal values, or ecological constraints. The OECD²³ makes it clear that allocation reform is about **sharing risks and opportunities** under increasing scarcity, making

²⁵ OECD, 2015. Water Resources Allocation: Sharing Risks and Opportunities, OECD Studies on Water. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264229631-en>

regimes more robust under both average and extreme conditions, and improving “adaptive efficiency” so they can adjust over time at least cost. Different pathways exist for reallocating water: some systems rely primarily on administrative changes (e.g., revising permits, adjusting priority rules, setting enforceable caps and drought restrictions), while others allow greater flexibility through mechanisms such as leasing, trading, or transferring entitlements, provided that safeguards exist to protect equity, ecosystems, and compliance.

In the Talanoia Water project, we explored how institutions can strengthen the capabilities needed to make reallocation both credible and fair, by making trade-offs visible and testing how rules perform under stress. In the Spanish case, we developed an actionable hydro-economic decision support system (DSS) to assess how tighter irrigation quotas, required to safeguard minimum environmental flows, would affect farm income, employment, and overall economic performance²⁶. The key value of this approach was not the model itself, but what it enabled for governance: by linking a hydrological model already used by basin authorities (AQUATOOL) with a behavioural microeconomic model of irrigators, the DSS made it possible to quantify who would lose, how much, and under what conditions, and to identify threshold effects that would not be evident through average-based analysis. The results showed that under “normal” conditions the economic impacts of protecting environmental flows were moderate, while under extreme droughts the same restrictions could push farming systems past a tipping point, producing disproportionate losses. In practice this means that any reform needs to be based on sequenced and contingency-based allocation rules rather than uniform restrictions across all conditions. In another piece of work, we explored a more flexible reallocation pathway: temporary water markets and trading mechanisms, as a way to improve allocative efficiency during scarcity²⁷. Our work showed that markets can, in principle, *shift water from lower-value to higher-value uses* in drought periods and help reduce the economic costs of shortages, but also made clear that such mechanisms are not “plug-and-play”. Their feasibility depends on strong enabling conditions: clear and enforceable entitlements, reliable measurement of actual use, institutional oversight to manage transactions, and safeguards to prevent inequitable outcomes or environmental degradation. The same governance logic was applied in the Lebanon case²⁸, where allocation reforms were stress-tested using monitoring-grade information: the project combined remote sensing estimates of biomass and water use with ensemble microeconomic models to test the impacts of progressively stricter quotas and water pricing reforms in the Upper Litani Basin. The analysis again showed non-linear responses and tipping

²⁶ Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Gil-García, L., Saiz-Santiago, P., 2021. An actionable hydroeconomic Decision Support System for the assessment of water reallocations in irrigated agriculture. A study of minimum environmental flows in the Douro River Basin, Spain. *Journal of Environmental Management* 298, 113432.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113432>

²⁷ Palomo-Hierro, S., Loch, A., Pérez-Blanco, C.D., 2022. Improving water markets in Spain: Lesson-drawing from the Murray-Darling Basin in Australia. *Agricultural Water Management* 259, 107224.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2021.107224>

²⁸ Sapino, F., Hazimeh, R., Dionisio Pérez-Blanco, C., Jaafar, H.H., 2024. Socioeconomic impact of agricultural water reallocation policies in the Upper Litani Basin (Lebanon): a remote sensing and microeconomic ensemble forecasting approach. *Agricultural Water Management* 296, 108805. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2024.108805>

points, where moderate restrictions were manageable, but deeper cuts led to sharp socio-economic disruption. This is a central lesson which we stress in this playbook: *equitable and efficient allocation reform requires not only political willingness, but the capability to measure use, anticipate distributional impacts, and design rules that remain fair and workable under drought extremes.*

Building capabilities for adaptation policy sequencing and implementation pathways. Adaptation policy sequencing matters because no single measure stays effective forever as warming level, climate variability, and compounding pressures increase. Many adaptation actions deliver strong benefits at today's risk levels, but their effectiveness can decline as hazards intensify, exposure grows, and thresholds are crossed, getting closer to *limits to adaptation*²⁹. Hence, adaptation becomes a process of progressively upgrading the strategy: measures that work under moderate stress (e.g., operational optimisation, efficiency improvements, or incremental infrastructure upgrades) may need to be complemented and eventually replaced by more robust options (e.g., allocation reform, demand restructuring, new governance arrangements, or major investment shifts). This creates an *adaptation pathway*: a sequence of actions that remain effective under increasing climate stress, until soft limits are reached and more transformative steps are required to prevent intolerable risks³⁰. According to the IPCC²⁸, these limits can be soft (options exist in principle, but are not currently feasible due to governance, finance, technology, or institutional constraints) or hard (no realistic adaptation options can avoid intolerable risks). Adaptation pathways are not only technical roadmaps, but implementation strategies that deliberately sequence reforms and investments: *first expanding capabilities to overcome soft limits through transformational adaptation*, while recognising that beyond certain warming levels and biophysical constraints, hard limits come into play.

Designing adaptation pathways is not just assembling a list of adaptation actions: it starts with setting a shared vision of the future and defining the level of resilience a basin or region aims to achieve. Without this, adaptation planning moves from identified risks to choosing siloed solutions³¹. A pathways approach,

²⁹ Martin, M.A., Boakye, E.A., Boyd, E., Broadgate, W., Bustamante, M., Canadell, J.G., Carr, E.R., Chu, E.K., Cleugh, H., Csevár, S., Daoudy, M., De Bremond, A., Dhimal, M., Ebi, K.L., Edwards, C., Fuss, S., Girardin, M.P., Glavovic, B., Hebden, S., Hirota, M., Hsu, H.-H., Huq, S., Ingold, K., Johannessen, O.M., Kameyama, Y., Kumarasinghe, N., Langendijk, G.S., Lissner, T., Lwasa, S., Machalaba, C., Maltais, A., Mathai, M.V., Mbow, C., McNamara, K.E., Mukherji, A., Murray, V., Mysiak, J., Okereke, C., Ospina, D., Otto, F., Prakash, A., Pulhin, J.M., Raju, E., Redman, A., Rigaud, K.K., Rockström, J., Roy, J., Schipper, E.L.F., Schlosser, P., Schulz, K.A., Schumacher, K., Schwarz, L., Scown, M., Šedová, B., Siddiqui, T.A., Singh, C., Sioen, G.B., Stammer, D., Steinert, N.J., Suk, S., Sutton, R., Thalheimer, L., Van Aalst, M., Van Der Geest, K., Zhao, Z.J., 2022. Ten new insights in climate science 2022. *Glob. Sustain.* 5, e20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2022.17>

³⁰ Ara Begum, R., R. Lempert, E. Ali, T.A. Benjaminsen, T. Bernauer, W. Cramer, X. Cui, K. Mach, G. Nagy, N.C. Stenseth, R. Sukumar, and P. Wester, 2022: Point of Departure and Key Concepts. In: *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lösschke, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 121–196, doi:10.1017/9781009325844.003.

³¹ Langendijk, G.S., Boon, E., Goosen, H., Jeuken, A., Castresana, S.Z., Cerezo, N.P., Mysiak, J., Kapetas, L., 2025. Ambition setting through climate services to drive climate resilient development. *Climate Services* 38, 100556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2025.100556>

by contrast, helps decision-makers sequence actions over time, anticipate when current measures will no longer be sufficient, and plan the enabling reforms and investments needed to move to the next step. Ambition setting explores alternative futures to unlock coordinated change toward climate-resilient development.

An example of the “pathways-building” approach is the *Regional Resilience Journey* (RRJ) developed under the Mission Adaptation [Pathways2Resilience](#) initiative, combines a structured methodological framework with cascading funds to help subnational governments move from risk awareness to ready-to-implement transformation plans. The RRJ is designed as an adaptable planning cycle that supports regions in shifting from reactive, incremental adaptation toward transformational adaptation, by guiding them through three core phases: (1) preparing the ground (establishing a baseline, understanding the system, and assessing risks and capabilities), (2) building a shared vision (ensuring ownership, exploring possible futures, co-creating a vision and specifying the logic of change), and (3) designing pathways (identifying and appraising options, building a portfolio of interventions, and preparing for implementation through action planning and monitoring, evaluation and learning). The RRJ builds the capabilities required for sequencing and implementation, not only for planning: it promotes systems thinking, and “portfolio” approaches that combine technical measures with institutional, social, and behavioural levers. It also emphasises that transformational adaptation is iterative rather than linear, with experimentation, reflection, and repeated updates as risks and capacities evolve.

3.3 Mobilise finance and align incentives

3.3.1 Why investment stalls (financial and behavioural barriers)

Financial barriers to adaptation are not only, or even primarily, about capital availability. Rather, they reflect structural capability gaps that make policy reforms difficult to sustain, and investments in water infrastructure less attractive to private investors. Partly, this is due to the *inadequate recovery of water service costs* through tariffs and taxes, which directly affects the ability to fund operation, maintenance, and the investments needed to adapt infrastructure to changing conditions. As a result, utilities, irrigation consortia, and basin authorities often struggle to maintain and modernise water assets or build resilience. This creates a structural dependence on public grants and subsidies, which are limited, competitive, and typically short term. Without predictable and stable revenue streams, organisations lack the financial credibility required to mobilise long-term finance, delaying investments in resilience, innovation, and broader system transformation.

Furthermore, investments are exposed regulatory uncertainty, market fluctuations, and climate-driven uncertainty in system performance such as variability in agricultural yields or the volume and reliability of water supply and sanitation services. All this makes future revenues uncertain. Most financial systems are not designed to handle this type of long-term, climate-driven uncertainty, and investors tend to avoid projects whose benefits are uncertain, delayed, or difficult to monetise, even if these projects are

contributing to improve resilience. Risk aversion disproportionately affects investments in areas such as water reuse, nature-based solutions, ecosystem restoration, and adaptive infrastructure, which may deliver strong long-term benefits but lack stable short-term returns on investments. The result is a bias toward conventional, low-risk projects and against innovation, experimentation, and transformation.

Another challenge is the difficulty of **valuing and internalising non-market benefits**. Many of the most important water adaptation investments, such as wetland restoration, floodplain reconnection, aquifer recharge, or ecosystem protection, generate public goods, including flood protection, improved water quality, biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, and avoided future damages. These benefits do not generate conventional cash flows and are therefore often perceived as high-risk or “non-bankable.” As a result, such investments rely almost entirely on public funding, blended finance, or dedicated programmes rather than mainstream investment channels. This reflects not only a market failure, but also a capability gap in designing financial instruments, valuation frameworks, and business models that can translate public value into investable structures.

Public water investments compete with other essential public priorities such as healthcare, education, housing, and security. Budgetary pressures limit fiscal space for long-term adaptation: water resilience investments are postponed because seen as less urgent than immediate social or political needs, even though long-term consequences may be severe. Upfront costs weigh more heavily than future benefits, and delayed returns are systematically undervalued. Water infrastructure upgrades, ecosystem restoration, and resilience investments often require high capital expenditure with benefits accruing gradually over decades. In financial systems and investment frameworks, these projects struggle to compete with sectors that offer faster, clearer, and more predictable returns, such as energy, transport, or mobility.

As a bottom line, the challenge is not simply mobilising more funding, but building the capabilities to structure finance, manage risk, value public benefits, protect long-term investment priorities, and govern distributional impacts. Without these capabilities, financial systems tend to favour incremental, low-risk, short-term investments and marginal improvements, while transformational reforms in water management remain structurally difficult to finance, scale, and sustain.

3.3.2 How to unlock scale (financing, risk-sharing, and markets)

Building capabilities to align economic and financial instruments with water resilience goals. A wide range of economic and financial instruments is already used in managing water, including tariffs and taxes, abstraction charges, tradable rights, subsidies, risk-transfer instruments, public grants, and blended finance structures. In practice, however, these instruments often operate in isolation, pursue narrow objectives, or reflect legacy priorities rather than current and future climate risks. Building financial capabilities therefore does not necessarily start with creating new instruments, but with aligning existing ones around clear water resilience goals. This requires ensuring that pricing, funding, and risk-sharing

mechanisms actively support long-term sustainability, equitable access, ecosystem protection, and climate robustness, rather than reinforcing short-term or fragmented responses.

Our research has provided *concrete, practice-oriented examples* of how financial capabilities can be built to better align economic instruments with water resilience goals. We have demonstrated how pricing and cost recovery, when supported by robust analytical tools, can move beyond revenue generation to actively shape water use behaviour and allocation outcomes³². Using hydro-economic modelling, we have shown how estimating the full resource cost of water, including opportunity costs, allows decision-makers to explore the economic and environmental implications of volumetric pricing in an irrigation-dependent basin. These results also show that full cost recovery can deliver meaningful reductions in water demand and help rebalance allocations toward sustainability. Similarly, we showed that pricing can serve as a behavioural incentive, internalise scarcity signals and support more efficient and resilient allocation.

We also explored how risk-sharing and market-based instruments can strengthen financial resilience under climate uncertainty. The climate-sensitive, index-based drought insurance scheme tested in the Cega River Basin demonstrated that insurance can remain actuarially feasible and affordable even under deep climate uncertainty when supported by scenario analysis and stress testing³³. This shows how risk-transfer instruments can complement regulation and public finance by stabilising incomes and reducing vulnerability during droughts.

In parallel, other studies examined more structural market mechanisms. The research shows that the effectiveness of water markets depends not only on price signals, but also on reducing information and transaction costs through appropriate institutional design³⁴. It also demonstrates that a price-discrimination water bank can significantly lower the public cost of water buybacks while generating surplus to fund environmental objectives³⁵. These examples highlight the importance of building capabilities to model trade-offs, manage risk, design incentives, and embed equity considerations, so that financial tools support, and not limit, transformational adaptation.

³² Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Sapino, F., 2022. Economic Sustainability of Irrigation-Dependent Ecosystem Services Under Growing Water Scarcity. Insights From the Reno River in Italy. *Water Resources Research* 58, e2021WR030478. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR030478>.

Sapino, F., Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Saiz-Santiago, P., 2022. A Hydro-Economic Model to Calculate the Resource Costs of Agricultural Water Use and the Economic and Environmental Impacts of Their Recovery. *Water Econs. Policy* 08, 2240012. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2382624X22400124>

³³ Agudo-Domínguez, A., Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Gil-García, L., Ortega, J.A., Dasgupta, S., 2022. Climate-sensitive hydrological drought insurance for irrigated agriculture under deep uncertainty. Insightful results from the Cega River Basin in Spain. *Agricultural Water Management* 274, 107938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107938>

³⁴ Sapino, F., Haer, T., Saiz-Santiago, P., Pérez-Blanco, C.D., 2023. A multi-agent cellular automata model to explore water trading potential under information transaction costs. *Journal of Hydrology* 618, 129195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.129195>

³⁵ Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Sapino, F., Saiz-Santiago, P., 2023. First-degree price discrimination water bank to reduce reacquisition costs and enhance economic efficiency in agricultural water buyback. *Ecological Economics* 205, 107694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107694>

Balancing efficiency, equity, and resilience is fundamental. Tariffs and charges must generate predictable revenues for operation, maintenance, and adaptation investments, while also sending credible signals about scarcity and environmental limits. This, in turn, requires that economic instruments be designed for, and embedded within, reformed governance frameworks. Pricing, trading, and compensation mechanisms can function effectively only when water rights, abstraction limits, and environmental objectives are clearly defined and enforced. Where allocation rules remain ambiguous or over-allocated, financial instruments risk legitimising unsustainable use rather than correcting it.

Building capabilities to internalise the value of nature and ecosystem services in water management.

Efforts to internalise the value of nature and ecosystem services start with building the capabilities to identify, quantify, or access existing estimates of ecosystem services in ways that are decision- and business-relevant. This means connecting ecological conditions and ecosystem services to water policy outcomes, such as reduced peak flows, improved baseflows, or enhanced groundwater recharge, and then translating these outcomes into estimates of avoided costs, risk-reduction benefits, or gains in service reliability. We built these capabilities across several pilot basins through analytical work that framed ecosystem restoration as a part of water management strategies, for example, by using wetlands and restored floodplains to attenuate floods, or by enhancing infiltration areas to support groundwater recharge. In collaboration with the NATURANCE initiative, which was set up to explore solutions that combine nature restoration with insurance or insurance-linked securities, we examined how restoring marginal or low-value agricultural land could reduce downstream flood risk and how reduced insurance premiums for those whose risk was lowered could be used to compensate farmers³⁶. Working in a similar but more direct way are *payments for ecosystem services*, such as schemes that compensate landowners for maintaining or restoring forested infiltration areas designed to enhance groundwater recharge, improve water quality, and deliver other services, supported through environmental funds or tariff-based contributions from water users who benefit from those services³⁷. In another study connected to Italian lab we have shown that modern irrigation practices, apart of improving on-farm water efficiency, can reduce return flows that sustain downstream ecosystems, creating negative externalities that are not reflected in market decisions. Compensating farmers for maintaining ecosystem-supporting water flows can thus preserve critical ecosystem services while remaining economically viable across climate scenarios. This example shows that internalised environmental costs (and benefits) can help to align private incentives with system-wide water and ecosystem outcomes³⁸.

³⁶ Bastanzi, G., Biddau, F., Ceolotto, S., Mysiak, J., Staccione, A., 2025. Concept Note - Boosting flood resilience through controlled flooding, community insurance and nature-based solutions.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.18018414>

³⁷ Etifor, 2018. Bosco Limite, outdoor nature. URL <https://www.etifor.com/en/portfolio/boscolimite/> (accessed 1.27.26).

³⁸ Pérez-Blanco, C.D., Sapino, F., 2022. Economic Sustainability of Irrigation-Dependent Ecosystem Services Under Growing Water Scarcity. Insights From the Reno River in Italy. *Water Resources Research* 58, e2021WR030478. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR030478>

However, across our pilots a common lesson emerged: the main gap is not a lack of interest in nature-based solutions, but a lack of capabilities to design viable business models around them. Schemes that internalise the value of ecosystem services require the capacity to innovate both policy and business models, and to reframe nature restoration as a form of risk-reducing investment rather than as a purely environmental cost. What ultimately becomes investable or insurable are specific ecosystem functions that can be monitored, verified, and contractually linked to reduced losses or improved system performance. Achieving this calls for capabilities to translate ecosystem benefits into concrete incentives, supported by regulatory frameworks that effectively shape decisions and investment behaviour, as well as the ability to clearly define service providers and beneficiaries, establish credible monitoring and verification systems, and manage long-term contractual arrangements. Without these capabilities, nature-based approaches tend to remain dependent on short-term grants and struggle to scale. When they are in place, however, ecosystem restoration can move from the margins of policy to the core of water allocation, investment planning, and risk management, supporting resilience, equity, and long-term system viability.

Building capabilities to mobilise private capital and blend it with public finance for water adaptation.

Across regions, a growing gap has emerged between the scale of water infrastructure investment needed and the funding currently mobilised. Closing this gap will require investment far beyond current public spending levels. Water projects are typically capital-intensive, long-lived, and exposed to regulatory, demand, and climate uncertainty, making them unattractive to private investors in the absence of de-risking mechanisms. This means that bridging the water investment gap depends on the ability to blend public and private finance, using public funds, guarantees, and development finance to crowd in private capital³⁹. In the Talanoa Water project, we have not directly address large-scale water infrastructure finance or private capital mobilisation, but we recognise how important this challenge is for transformational adaptation.

The *European Water Resilience Strategy*⁴⁰ recognises that achieving water security under climate change will require mobilising substantially more finance, including through blended public–private approaches. Finance, investment, and infrastructure are identified as key enabling pillars, alongside governance, digitalisation, research and innovation, and preparedness. This underscores the need to make water resilience projects more attractive and viable for a wider range of investors. To this end, the EC promotes closer cooperation with financial institutions, notably the European Investment Bank, using public funding, guarantees, and technical assistance to de-risk projects, improve bankability, and crowd in private capital for innovation, infrastructure upgrades, and resilience measures. As part of this agenda, the EC is developing a **Water Resilience Investment Accelerator** to help close the gap between technically sound water solutions and their ability to attract finance at scale. The Accelerator is designed to support selected

³⁹ World Economic Forum, 2025. Bridging the \$6.5 Trillion Water Infrastructure Gap: A Playbook. World Economic Forum, Geneva.

⁴⁰ EC, 2025. European Water Resilience Strategy. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions.

pilot cases by bringing together regions, municipalities, utilities, solution providers, and investors to develop bankable and replicable investment models. Rather than financing infrastructure directly, it focuses on building investment-ready projects through advisory support on blended finance structures, risk-sharing arrangements, and project preparation, with a focus on areas such as water efficiency, digitalisation, nature-based solutions, and circular water systems. In doing so, it addresses a key capability gap faced by many water actors: turning resilience needs and public-value benefits into investable propositions that can mobilise private capital while safeguarding long-term public objectives. The EU Mission on Adaptation also creates incentives for increased investment in adaptation, including in the water sector. An upcoming call will offer cascading funds, similar to the support for climate risk assessment and adaptation pathways mentioned earlier, but at a much larger scale, to help implement bankable adaptation projects⁴¹. The Talanoia Water team is contributing to policy dialogue on how these instruments could be designed and is advising regional and river basin authorities on how to plan projects and position themselves to secure this support.

4 Conclusions

This playbook was developed through discussions held during the international workshops in Venice, Italy, on 6–7 May 2025, and in Istanbul, Türkiye, on 4–5 November 2025, as well as during the online Webstival held on 5 September 2025⁴². These workshops and the webinar brought together representatives from the Talanoia Water stakeholder organisations and guests from other innovation projects to discuss the key barriers to adaptation and the solutions needed to foster transformative change.

Rather than focusing the discussion on individual adaptation actions, this playbook emphasises the **capabilities needed to drive change** in how water is managed, how incentives for water conservation are designed, and how knowledge about water-related risks and opportunities is generated and used in decision-making. These capabilities constitute what are often referred to as enabling conditions for deeply rooted change in the way persistent causes of water management challenges, and the inequalities that exacerbate them, are addressed. We deliberately speak of capabilities rather than abstract enabling conditions **to stress the agency of different actors** in shaping, building, and sustaining these conditions through policy, investment, and practice. To our knowledge, this guidebook is one of the first one to explicitly focus on **capabilities as vectors of change**.

We have elaborated nine specific capabilities across the three categories, drawing on our own experience and practical work. These should not be seen as exhaustive: other lessons and capability gaps exist that we have not fully addressed or were unable to capture within the scope of this work. We therefore encourage

⁴¹ EC, 2025. Supporting financing of local adaptation actions with combination of public funding and private financing HORIZON-MISS-2026-01-CLIMA-07. [Link](#)

⁴² For more information see Mysiak, J., 2025. Fourth 12-month exploitation, dissemination and communication report (No. Deliverable D5.6). CMCC – Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change, Bologna, Italy.

further research, experimentation, and more in-depth training focused on how these capabilities can be built and sustained in different contexts. Most importantly, we see this playbook as a starting point for further work on developing self- and peer-assessment approaches for capabilities for change, potentially to be carried out jointly with other on-the-ground innovation actions and policy initiatives. We also believe that these capability areas can be translated into practical indicators that can be reported and tracked when monitoring progress on adaptation at the river basin scale.

- Building capacities for access, management, and integrated analysis of diverse datasets
- Building capacities to anticipate service disruption, stress-test critical infrastructure, and assess resilience to shocks
- Building capacities for monitoring operational compliance and adaptation performance.
- Building capacities for inclusive, bottom-up water governance and all-of-society engagement
- Building capacities for equitable allocation and efficient water use
- Building capacities for adaptation policy sequencing and implementation pathways
- Building capacities to align economic and financial instruments with water resilience goals
- Building capacities to internalise the value of nature and ecosystem services in water management
- Building capacities to mobilise private capital and blend it with public finance for water adaptation